

Gond

also known as “Koi”, “Koitur”, “Hill Maria”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

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Entry tags: Religion, Indic Religious Traditions, Hinduism

Bastar District, India, is home to several indigenous groups including the Gond; this entry focuses on the Hill Marias circa 1938. The Hill Marias are very isolated geographically, and are as a result less acculturated. Their religious beliefs are of the Hindu family, "yet at the same time it is but little 'Hinduized'. It remains a special and characteristic faith, a logical entity which can be described and recognized" (Verrier, 1947: 1740). The Hill Maria religious beliefs are interwoven with social, civil, and political aspects of life and should be considered a part of the society as a whole.

Date Range: 1875 CE - 1910 CE

Region: Abujhmar hills of Bastar State

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

Abujhmar hills of Bastar State, India ca. 1900. (Bastar is now a district of Chhattisgarh State)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw32-001>

– Source 1 Description: Grigson, W. V. (Wilfred Vernon), and Verrier Elwin. 1949. "Maria Gonds Of Bastar." London: Oxford University Press.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw32-002>

– Source 2 Description: Elwin, Verrier. 1947. "Muria And Their Ghotul." Bombay: Oxford University Press.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/ehrafe/>

– Source 3 Description: eHRAF World Cultures, Gond Collection (AW32)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Hill Maria have cultural contact with other religious groups through exchange with Hindu and Mohammedan traders. Among the indigenous groups in Bastar state [now Bastar district], the Hill Maria are most isolated and least acculturated with outside groups. (See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Chapters I-III, and XVII). See questions below for more details on cultural contact.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The Hill Maria have a neutral relationship with the State [now Bastar District] (Grigson and Verrier, 1949: 295), and a neutral trading relationship with those who travel into the isolated hills (Grigson and Verrier, 1949: 50).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: "Peace has reigned in the Abujhmar hills from time immemorial, and no question of defense arises when a village is built" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:101).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: The Gond have a history of being exploited by Bastar [formerly a State], and from 1908-1910, several tribes banded together and broke out in rebellion. However, the Hill Marias abstained from these battles (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:15).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Hill Maria religion is best described as shared beliefs and practices, as opposed to an organized religion. Hereditary clan membership will determine an individual's totem and clan-god(s), but there is no set process for assigning religious affiliation (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, Chapter X: The Earth, The Clan-god, And The Village Mother).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The Hill Maria religion is best described as shared beliefs and practices, as opposed to an organized religion. Because the religion is so informal, there is no active recruitment of new members (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, Chapter X: The Earth, The Clan-god, And The Village Mother).

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Hill Marias do not have an official, organized political hierarchy beyond the level of the clan. As one of the several indigenous groups living in Bastar State [now a district], the Hill Marias are technically under the jurisdiction of the State; for the isolated Hill Marias, this is more of a meaningless formality. Although the Hill Maria belief system is interwoven with civil organization and social structure, the polity does not officially support the religion. (See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Chapter XVII, various pages including 284-286).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 11500

Notes: Principal ethnographic source (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:28) estimate a total population of about 11,500 Hill Marias, consisting of about 150-160 villages. Because all Hill Marias subscribe to the same religious beliefs, the total population can also be considered as the religious group.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: Because all Hill Marias follow the same belief system, the entire society would be considered adherents of the religious group.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: "Muria religion is undoubtedly a religion of the Hindu family with special affinities to its Shaivite interpretation, yet at the same time it is but little 'Hinduized'. It remains a special and characteristic faith, a logical entity which can be described and recognized. It acknowledges a large number of deities whom it pictures in a simple and homely manner. It has a definite priesthood and a body of mediums who communicate with the gods while in a state of trance. It erects shrines and temples to the gods and builds small huts for the tendance and placation of the dead. It consecrates every rural activity by sacrifice and a sacramental meal. It purifies and protects the village by a series of ceremonies, and it directs its beneficial power against the energies of witch and warlock" (Verrier, 1947:174).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "...the clan-priest is generally not the clan headman even in the Abujhmar hills tracts where the clan-area has become the modern pargana [political unit]. He may or may not be a person of ability and influence. He should be the medium, into whose body the clan-god enters and through whose mouth the god makes his will known to his clan. The secular pargana headman is a man of far more influence; and in the villages the kasyeq-gaita and the perma are religious headmen in a way that the clan-priest seldom is in the clan; often the same man is both religious headman and secular headman

(gaita, peda), and these functions were probably always combined before the growing interference of the State with village life and the excessive demands for forced labour and supplies began to make the secular headmanship a burden to be avoided by the true leader of the village and put on to the village simpleton" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:195).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for an official hierarchy among religious leaders (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:284).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: The clan-priest "should be the medium, into whose body the clan-god enters and through whose mouth the god makes his will known to the clan" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:195).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: The position of religious headman is hereditary, acquired through membership in a high-ranking family (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:284).

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Among the Hill Marias, the kasyeq-gaita (religious headman) is essentially "powerless to effect anything without the consent of the village elders" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:284).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 66, there are no large or impressive structures present among the Hill Maria (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 66, there are no large or impressive structures present among the Hill Maria (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic and Verrier, 1947, Chapter Six, Section III: The Soul And Its Fate

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "A man has two souls: one always remains with him; the other, a smaller one, leaves him in sleep and its adventures are what we call dreams. When a man dies the soul remains near the house and when a child is born we say 'A visitor has come' meaning that the soul has returned to its own place" (Informant cited in Verrier, 1947:144).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail; Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "All Marias agree that the dead are somewhere underground; men, animals, trees, and perhaps rivers and streams have in them jiwa, a principal of life, and some say that when a man dies his jiwa goes to Pogho Bhum, the sky, while that part which is cremated or buried goes below the earth and is his hanal [ghost]" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "All Marias agree that the dead are somewhere underground; men, animals, trees, and perhaps rivers and streams have in them jiwa, a principal of life, and some say that when a man dies his jiwa goes to Pogho Bhum, the sky, while that part which is cremated or buried goes below the earth and is his hanal [ghost]" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: A belief in reincarnation is somewhat but minimally present among the Hill Maria, but this belief is not a prevalent aspect of the Hill maria religion. "There are traces of an embryo belief in reincarnation in the practice among Hill Marias of examining a new-born baby to see if it has the same birth-marks as a dead ancestor and, if so, of naming it after the ancestor if of the same sex, or his spouse if of the other sex" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The ordinary rule throughout the Abujhmar hills is to cremate the bodies of headmen and elders of influence and standing and of their wives, and to bury all others" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:271).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "The ordinary rule throughout the Abujhmar hills is to cremate the bodies of headmen and elders of influence and standing and of their wives, and to bury all others" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:271).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The ordinary rule throughout the Abujhmar hills is to cremate the bodies of headmen and elders of influence and standing and of their wives, and to bury all others" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:271).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "Both for burial and for cremation most Hill Marias place the body in the grave or on the pyre with the head, face upwards, towards the sunrise and the feet towards the sunset; the Usendi clan, however, reverses this" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:272).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Notes: "They close the eyes of the corpse, and lift it on to a rough wicker-work bier, covering it over with a length of cloth. It is burned or buried with the clothes and jewelry that were on it at death. For the last rites the body is not washed or otherwise prepared, but is left just as it was composed after death" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:271).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: When it can be afforded, either a chicken, pig, or cow (depending on the specific clan) is sacrificed at the burial ground (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:276).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority on the Hill Maria has found no evidence for human sacrifices (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:193).

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: When it can be afforded, either a chicken, pig, or cow (depending on the specific clan) is sacrificed at the burial ground (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:276).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "The property thus brought to the grave is either buried with the body or hung up on saja trees over or near the grave, or on the fence or hanal-gutta posts erected around or in front of the grave" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:271).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "...the dead man's spare clothes, if any, his ornaments, his axe (but not his bow and arrows), his hoe (gudari), his cot and his dancing clothes and ornaments; generally all or some of his cooking pots are also taken to the grave" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:272).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present among the Hill Maria. For headmen and elders of influence, the body is cremated rather than buried. See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Chapter XVI: Death and Funeral Ceremonies, Section A: Hill Marias.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Bodies are buried or cremated in the funeral grounds (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:272).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The most important supernatural beings to the Hill Maria are the Clan-gods, and the spirits of the dead. See questions below for more detail. (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It appears that the Gond have a supreme high gods, Ispural, but it is unclear if the specific tribe of the Hill Marias believe in and worship Ispural. "They sometimes say that they have heard of a god named Ispural [supreme being in other Muria tribes] living in Pogho-bhum, but that they do not worship him" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:230). "Only around Orcha and a few neighbouring Chhota Dongar pargana [towns, essentially] Hill Maria villages did I find any idea of a vague Supreme Being, Ispural, who would perhaps punish evil-doers somewhere after death; but no one could say who or where Ispural was, or where the sinful would be judged and punished" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of deceased humans are referred to as "hanal", which translates to "departed". See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Departed are regarded by the Hill Maria as having the power to influence sowing and harvesting, and are therefore propitiated at seed-time by the wiji-ahk or 'seed-leaves' ceremony and at the new-eating festivals by the wives offering the new grains before the Pot of the Departed after cooking them on the Hearth of the Departed, and by the husband in the morning depositing three leaves with the new food by the roadside as offerings to them" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:222).

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The old prejudice against sexual intercourse in the house, still alive in the remotest Abujhmar villages, was due to a belief that it was disrespectful to the hanal [ghost]; it survives everywhere, therefore, to discourage strangers from adultery with the wife in the husband's absence, and it is believed that such adultery entails the immediate wrath of the hanal" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Hill Marias have a vague dread of evil spirits of the mountains, which they call rau..." (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:206). Additionally, each clan has a clan-god.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the only rau to whom I have heard a name given by Hill Marias is Raja Rau, the demon of the Raughat pass in Antagarh tahsil, held to be a very Raja of the rau because he caused mountain-sickness to the first European surveyor seen in Bastar. All Marias also speak with fear of a water-witch in the form of a great serpent, known as

Tondetaras, haunting river rapids and waterfalls, the mere sight of whom is fatal" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:206).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear if the rau or water-witch cause harm randomly or to specifically punish humans.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic. "...the Departed [souls of the dead] are believed to be vitally interested in human affairs. They are naturally conservative and are particularly interested in maintaining the laws and customs of their tribe. Any breach of the taboos relating to women is specially hateful to them" (Verrier, 1947:146).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "The hanal are the guardians of the rules of taboo, of which those forbidding individuals to start agricultural operations until the appropriate ceremony has been held and all the village is able to get to work together serve to strengthen and maintain the traditions of village co-operation" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic, Chapter XII, Section A: The Cult of The Departed

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Women

Notes: "Women are the soil in which is sown the seed of the race, and the hanal naturally, therefore, punish infringement of the taboos which safeguard them, such as the menstruation taboos, the taboo against sexual intercourse during pregnancy, and those requiring the wife to remain secluded for a month after delivery" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

– Yes [specify]: Adultery

Notes: "The old prejudice against sexual intercourse in the house, still alive in the remotest Abujhmar villages, was due to a belief that it was disrespectful to the hanal [human ghost]; it survives everywhere, therefore, to discourage strangers from adultery with the wife in the husband's absence, and it is believed that such adultery entails the immediate wrath of the hanal" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery is punished, according to Muria opinion, by some form of dropsy which is brought upon the offenders by the Departed, to whom elaborate offerings must be made before a cure can be effected. So also in a case of murder or grievous hurt peace can only be made between the two families if peace is made first between their ancestors" (Verrier, 1947:146).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic, Chapter XII, Section A: The Cult of The Departed

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: "The old prejudice against sexual intercourse in the house, still alive in the remotest Abujhmar villages, was due to a belief that it was disrespectful to the hanal [human ghost]; it survives everywhere, therefore, to discourage strangers from adultery with the wife in the husband's absence, and it is believed that such adultery entails the immediate wrath of the hanal" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: "Incest within the clan is regarded as specially insulting to the Anga [clan-god] and before the guilty can be forgiven offerings must be made to it. If they do not do this the offenders' bodies will swell and their eyes burst" (Verrier, 1947:191).

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Exogamy

Notes: "As the clan-god is looked upon as the first ancestor of the clan, this association is not unnatural, and so the clan-god will help the Departed to protect the household and to punish breaches of the taboos, and, above all, of the laws of exogamy" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "The hanal are the guardians of the rules of taboo, of which those forbidding individuals to start agricultural operations until the appropriate ceremony has been held and all the village is able to get to work together serve to strengthen and maintain the traditions of village co-operation" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts of deceased humans, Clan-gods, and other spirits can all punish (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, various pages, including 195-200, 222-224). See Below for more details and specific aspects of supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts of deceased humans, Clan-gods, and other spirits can all punish (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, various pages, including 195-200, 222-224).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: There is no clear belief in a supreme high god among the Hill Maria (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224, 230). "Only around Orcha and a few neighbouring Chhota Dongar pargana [towns, essentially] Hill Maria villages did I find any idea of a vague Supreme Being, Ispural, who would perhaps punish evil-doers somewhere after death; but no one could say who or where Ispural was, or where the sinful would be judged and punished" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts of deceased humans, Clan-gods, and other spirits can all punish (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, various pages, including 195-200, 222-224).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: ...the Departed [souls of the dead] are believed to be vitally interested in human affairs. They are naturally conservative and are particularly interested in maintaining the laws and customs of their tribe. Any breach of the taboos relating to women is specially hateful to them" (Verrier, 1947:146).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The hanal are the guardians of the rules of taboo, of which those forbidding individuals to start agricultural operations until the appropriate ceremony has been held and all the village is able to get to work together serve to strengthen and

maintain the traditions of village co-operation" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: ...the Departed [souls of the dead] are believed to be vitally interested in human affairs. They are naturally conservative and are particularly interested in maintaining the laws and customs of their tribe. Any breach of the taboos relating to women is specially hateful to them" (Verrier, 1947:146).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The hanal are the guardians of the rules of taboo, of which those forbidding individuals to start agricultural operations until the appropriate ceremony has been held and all the village is able to get to work together serve to strengthen and maintain the traditions of village co-operation" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:223).

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: It appears that the rau and the water-witches punish randomly. "...the only rau to whom I have heard a name given by Hill Marias is Raja Rau, the demon of the Raughat pass in Antagarh tahsil, held to be a very Raja of the rau because he caused mountain-sickness to the first European surveyor seen in Bastar. All Marias also speak with fear of a water-witch in the form of a great serpent, known as Tondetaras, haunting river rapids and waterfalls, the mere sight of whom is fatal" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:206).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "Only around Orcha and a few neighbouring Chhota Dongar pargana [towns, essentially] Hill Maria villages did I find any idea of a vague Supreme Being, Ispural, who would perhaps punish evil-doers somewhere after death; but no one could say who or where Ispural was, or where the sinful would be judged and punished" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:224).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more specific details (Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV, various pages, including 195-200, 222-224)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:222)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: "Incest within the clan is regarded as specially insulting to the Anga [clan-god] and before the guilty can be forgiven offerings must be made to it. If they do not do this the offenders' bodies will swell and their eyes burst" (Verrier, 1947:191).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Throughout India the villagers dread and take endless trouble to placate the Matal or Village Mothers. These dangerous and malignant beings are the cause of disease, domestic tragedy and accident" (Verrier, 1947:168).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For a discussion on norms and taboos, particularly those with religious explanations, see Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Part IV: Religion and Magic, Chapter XII, Section A: The Cult of The Departed

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "The Muria believe that sexual congress is a good thing; it does you good; it is healthy and beautiful; when performed by the right people...at the right time (outside the menstrual period and avoiding forbidden days), and in the right place (within the ghotul [ritual building] walls where no sin can be committed), it is the happiest and best thing in life" (Verrier, 1947:419). Verrier (1947:420) notes that the Muris require priests to remain celibate on various occasions, but "the rule does not seem to be due to any special regard for celibacy as such or belief in its power; it is rather connected with the dread of the menstruous woman".

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: "It is taboo to eat any of the new crops until the appropriate new-eating festival has been celebrated" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:137). However, this is a taboo, and not a membership requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority on the Hill Maria has found no evidence for human sacrifices (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:193).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority on the Hill Maria has found no evidence for human sacrifices (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:193).

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority on the Hill Maria has found no evidence for human sacrifices (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:193).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: There is not a strong value on land and property among the Hill Maria. This fact, combined with the absence of any evidence for the sacrifice of property, leads to the assumption that membership in the Hill Maria religion does not require sacrifice of property. (See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, various pages, including 293-295).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Grigson and Verrier (1949) give many example of small-scale rituals among the Hill Maria, but it is unclear how mandatory these ceremonies are.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Hill Maria have a pandum [religious festival] three to four times a year as an essential preliminary to acts of gathering/harvesting (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:137). However, the obligatory nature of these ceremonies is not clear.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Gond have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). The Hill Maria are best described as an informal chiefdom, with the political unit existing at the clan level. Leadership is hereditary and based on a hierarchy of lineages. Although varying from clan to clan, power is typically exercised through a combination of a council of elders, a religious headman, and a secular headman.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: In the case of the Hill Maria, the religious group and society are coterminous. "There is no system of training Hill Maria children corresponding to the Gotul or Dormitory system of the Murias, except in the northernmost Hill Maria parganas [political unit similar to a village/town] of Padalbhun and Nurbhum. In the greater part of the Maria country, children learn simply by accompanying and imitating their parents and the elder boys of the village" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:267).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: In the case of the Hill Maria, the religious group and society are extremely interwoven. For food storage, the villagers "generally construct a row of granaries (manda or wijja-dodi) on piles at the side or rear of the main village street, sometimes nearer the penda fields than the village; this row can hardly be called a 'common granary', as each villager has his own granary in the row for his own private food and seed store, the granaries being built together only for convenience, as they can then be watched at night by one watchman for the whole village, sleeping in a special hut at the side of the granaries or under a granary" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:102).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no secular institution among the Hill Maria that provides public food storage. Additionally, the State of Bastar [now a district] does not provide public food storage. (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:102).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: In the case of the Hill Maria, the religious group and society are essentially coterminous. The only form of transportation infrastructure in Hill Maria villages are have simple footpaths. "Certain well-defined tracks through the hills are cleared annually by the villagers; these often avoid the actual village sites, to which side tracks connect them. There are no carts in the hills, and therefore the tracks

are only foot-paths, generally wide enough only for a party to walk in single file, though at the periodic clearings the grass is cut down to a width of two or three feet on each side of the path" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:101).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The State of Bastar [now a district] traditionally exploited Gonds into labor requirements, which sometimes included the construction of transportation infrastructure (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:15-17). However, the Hill Maria are very isolated, and had little to do with the State. The State did not provide transportation infrastructure to the Hill Maria, and there is no secular institution among the Hill Maria clans that provided transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bastar State [now a district] taxes clans of the Hill Maria. "One of the most remarkable features of the Bastar of 1927 was the extent to which tribal, village and caste panchayats [political units similar to towns] still regulated the religious and social life of the people, acted as intermediaries between them and the State and its zamindaris [officials] in meeting State demands for taxes, labour and supplies and in protecting the ryots from undue exactions, and exercised much de facto criminal and civil jurisdiction" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:284).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Depending on the particular clan, the religious headman might participate in overseeing legal and judicial matters (along with the secular headman and council of elders). Each clan has a different method of dealing with criminal and social violations, and there is not an official system of institutional judges. (See Grigson and Verrier, 1949, Chapter XVII, various pages including 284-296).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Hill Maria judicial system is comprised of religious and secular headmen, as well as a council of elders. The religion and civil aspects of life are very interwoven, but technically, the secular headman and council of elders would be considered a civil institution other than the religious group. Occasionally, the State (Bastar) [now a district] might get involved with serious criminal offences, but the Hill Maria usually resolve matters independently. In 1932, under the State Order, the "regular criminal courts of the State have been deprived of jurisdiction over the primitive tribes in cases of certain public nuisances, simple hurt and assault, thefts (except of cattle), of property worth Rs. 5 or less, mischief, trespass, house-trespass, bigamy, adultery and enticing a married woman from her

husband. The civil courts have been deprived of jurisdiction in claims for civil damages arising out of these criminal offences, and in simple money, grain and cattle claims up to Rs. 25 in value. All such cases are to be dealt with by the village panchayat [civil structure], the convening of which and the selection of the elders of which are left to the village headman" (Grigson and Verrier, 1949:295).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religion and polity are so intertwined, the religious group is essentially coterminous with the society. The Hill Maria are primarily agriculturalists, practicing shifting cultivation. Gathering, animal husbandry, and hunting provide additional sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Because the religion and polity are so intertwined, the religious group is essentially coterminous with the society. The Hill Maria are primarily agriculturalists, practicing shifting cultivation. Gathering, animal husbandry, and hunting provide additional sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.